

Silver-ion Catalysed Oxidation of Urea with Peroxodisulphate

M. C. Agrawal and S. P. Mushran

The kinetics of silver-ion catalysed decomposition of urea has been investigated. The total order of reaction is unity, being first order with respect to peroxodisulphate and zero order with respect to urea. Uncatalysed oxidation of urea is not possible with peroxodisulphate even at high temperatures. The energy of activation and entropy of activation for the silver-ion catalysed oxidation process have been found to be 12.3 kcal. mole⁻¹ and -32.35 e.u. respectively. A suitable mechanism involving formation of higher-valent silver intermediates for the oxidation of the substrate by peroxodisulphate has been formulated.

The strong oxidising capacity of peroxodisulphate in aqueous solutions is well known. The kinetics of oxidation of several organic and inorganic compounds has been investigated by several workers¹ and in several cases silver ions have been found to catalyse such reactions. Recently in these laboratories colloidal silver² has also been used to catalyse such oxidation processes. The kinetic investigation of the oxidation of organic nitrogen compounds by peroxodisulphate has, however, received very little attention so far. The present communication embodies the results on the kinetics of oxidation of urea by potassium peroxodisulphate, catalysed by silver ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

As the aqueous solution of potassium peroxodisulphate changed its strength slightly on keeping for a few days, the solution of the reagent (A.R., B.D.H.) was always prepared fresh before experiments. All other chemicals used were also of A.R., B.D.H. or extra pure quality and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Two solutions, one containing silver nitrate and urea and the other containing peroxodisulphate, were kept in a water thermostat separately and then mixed. After certain time intervals 5-ml portions were withdrawn by a pipette in a flask containing 10 ml of 2*N*-HCl. The amount of unconsumed peroxodisulphate was determined iodometrically as described by Szabo *et al*.³

One set of experimental data is presented in Table I. The first-order rate constants obtained were found to be fairly satisfactory, except for the first few constants where slight variations were observed.

1. House, "A Review on Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidations by Peroxydisulphate", 1962.
2. Virendra Singh, Doctoral Thesis, Allahabad University, 1964.
3. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1952, 135, 269.

TABLE I

Urea = 0.1*M*. K₂S₂O₈ = 0.02*M*. AgNO₃ = 0.001*M*. Temp. = 35° ± 0.1°.

Time.	Hypo.	$k/2.303 \times 10^4$ min.
0 min.	5.00 ml	..
40	4.70	6.72
80	4.42	6.70
120	4.22	6.14
160	4.04	5.78
200	3.82	5.84
240	3.64	5.74
280	3.44	5.80
320	3.20	6.06
360	3.04	5.92

Av. 5.89

or $k = 13.56 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Effect of Peroxodisulphate Concentration.—The reaction between urea and peroxodisulphate afforded fairly agreeable first-order rate constants. To know whether the reaction is truly of first order with respect to peroxodisulphate, different concentrations of the oxidant were employed. The effect of the various concentrations of peroxodisulphate on the reaction rate is shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Urea = 0.1 <i>M</i> .	AgNO ₃ = 0.001 <i>M</i> .	Temp. = 35° ± 0.1°.	
Initial conc. of oxidant (<i>M</i>) ..	0.01	0.02	0.04
$k \times 10^4$ (min.) ..	17.11	13.56	9.46

The rate constants thus appear to decrease with increasing concentration of peroxodisulphate. This decrease may be ascribed to the inhibiting effect of potassium ions which are known to inhibit peroxodisulphate oxidations of many organic substances, such as oxalic acid⁴ and glycerol⁵.

Effect of Urea Concentration.—Table III shows the effect of different concentrations of urea on the reaction rate.

TABLE III

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.02 <i>M</i> .	AgNO ₃ = 0.001 <i>M</i> .	Temp. = 35° ± 0.1°.		
Initial conc. of urea (<i>M</i>) ..	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.1
$k \times 10^4$ (min.) ..	14.37	14.11	13.72	53.46

The total order of the reaction was determined by the isolation method, using the expression:

$$\bar{n} = \log (k_1/k_2) / \log (c_1/c_2)$$

where k_1, k_2 are the rate constants at reductant concentrations c_1 and c_2 .

4. Gupta and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1958, **35**, 483.5. Mishra and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1964, **41**, 402.

The order of reaction thus comes out to be 0.02 from which the reaction is concluded to be of zero order with respect to urea. The same conclusion can be arrived at by noting the insignificant variation in rate constants in Table III for largely varying concentration of urea.

Effect of Concentration of Silver Ions.—The effect of three different concentrations of silver ions on the reaction was studied at three different temperatures (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Initial conc. of AgNO_3 .	First-order rate constants ($k \times 10^4$) at		
	35°.	40°.	45°.
0.001 M	13.56	18.60	25.08
0.002	25.81	36.96	48.75
0.004	53.47	71.46	98.90

The plots of the rate constants vs. silver nitrate concentrations at various temperatures are shown in Fig. 1. These are straight lines passing through the origin, from which it is inferred that the uncatalysed decomposition of urea by peroxodisulphate is not possible even at 45°.

FIG. 1

Activation Energy and Entropy of Activation.—Energy of activation was calculated graphically from the slope of the plots of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ at various silver-ion concentrations (Table V).⁷

From Table V the variation in the concentration of silver ions does not appear to have any effect on the energy of activation; its average value comes out to be 12.3 kcal. mole⁻¹. For this average value of energy of activation, the frequency factor and entropy of activation have been calculated to be 61.66×10^4 litres mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ and -32.35 e.u. for temperatures between 35° and 45°.

TABLE V

Initial conc. of AgNO ₃ (M)	..	0.001	0.002	0.004
Energy of activation (cal. mole ⁻¹)	..	12,180	12,430	12,260

DISCUSSION

The oxidation of urea by different oxidants usually involves the liberation of nitrogen. But it is not evolved quantitatively. With peroxodisulphate, urea yields carbon dioxide and nitrogen and the rupture of the valency bonds of all the carbon atoms thus appears to occur during the process of oxidation. The oxidation, however, takes place in presence of silver ions as catalyst and uncatalysed decomposition of urea is not possible with peroxodisulphate even at high temperatures. The process of oxidation may be represented as

the extent of oxidation depending on the concentration of the reactants.

For the catalytic oxidation of several organic compounds by peroxodisulphate in presence of silver ions, various mechanisms have been suggested in which the role of bivalent and trivalent silver intermediates has been emphasised. Yost⁶ believes the silver intermediates to be trivalent silver, but Malaguti⁷ suggests bivalent intermediates.

For the silver-ion catalysed decomposition of urea by peroxodisulphate, the monovalent silver ion is oxidised to bivalent or trivalent state and these higher valent states of silver act as oxidising agents for the reducing substrate. Thus the following steps are involved:

The formation of bivalent silver is suggested by the reaction :

The formation of such higher valent states of silver intermediates has been proposed by Mushran *et al.*⁸ for explaining the mechanism of various oxidation reactions catalysed by colloidal silver. The present results of investigation of the oxidation of urea show that the

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 152.

7. *Ann. Chem. (Rome)*, 1955, **41**, 241.

8. Under publication.

SILVER-ION CATALYSED OXIDATION OF UREA WITH PEROXODISULPHATE

rates of oxidation are proportional to the concentrations of peroxodisulphate and silver ions and independent of the concentration of the reducing substrate. Thus, for the silver-catalysed decomposition of urea by peroxodisulphate, the loss of the oxidant may be expressed as:

$$-d/dt (S_2O_8^{2-}) = k(S_2O_8^{2-}) (Ag^+)$$

The above equation indicates that the reaction is of zero order with respect to urea. Our experimental results also show that increasing concentration of urea does not affect the rate of its oxidation. The mechanism of the silver-ion catalysed oxidation of urea by peroxodisulphate therefore is

The above step involving two-electron transfer is the slow step which controls the rate of oxidation. This step is immediately followed by the fast step, leading to the oxidation of substrate (S) as

the oxygen being made available for the oxidation process by the interaction of higher-valent silver and solvent water.

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. Satya Prakash, D. Sc., for his kind interest in this investigation.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

Received February 11, 1965.